

Forming Future English Language Teachers' Grammatical Competence

Jumanazarov U.U.

Doctor of Philosophy in Pedagogical Sciences (PhD), Jizzakh State Pedagogical University

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Corresponding Author:
Jumanazarov U.U.

ABSTRACT

The article discusses the specific features, composition and models of grammatical competence in future English teachers, as well as the stages of formation of grammatical competence.

KEYWORDS: grammatical competence, sub-competition, model, competence, imitation, transformation, communicative, practice, relational ability, ability.

INTRODUCTION

In the scientific and methodological literature, we have observed the existence of definitions of grammatical competence that are diverse, but very close in content and complement each other. We have the opportunity to bring them here as much as we want. However, for this chapter of our study, the question arises here: what is grammatical competence and what are its possibilities in communicative competence in a foreign language (CCFL)? Below we will first try to describe some of our observations identified during the research process on the same issue. According to the European system of foreign language proficiency, “grammatical competence” is the ability to know and use the grammatical means of a language. This definition, in our opinion, does not reflect all the features of educational competence. We are referring here only to the ability to carry out effective activities of social significance. According to M. Canale and M. Swain, “grammatical competence” includes knowledge of lexical units and morphological rules, syntax, sentence semantics, and phonology [1]. If we approach this definition on the basis of an author's approach, it only mentions information about different rules that cannot allow students to conduct speaking activities in a foreign language without their own skills and abilities. Moreover, knowledge of lexical units is not the basis and object of grammatical competence. Because both have different goals, structure and structure, methods, lexical and grammatical competencies as a component of linguistic competencies were examined separately in this study, a number of ideas identified and validated in the experimental fields were also presented separately.

THE MAIN FINDINGS AND RESULTS

All of the above definitions of grammatical competence, on the one hand, do not fully express the basic definition of the

concept of educational competence, and on the other hand, interpret its structure and content differently. Although scholars have studied the problem from different perspectives and are ambivalent about the interpretation of the term “grammatical competence”, we have tried to summarize the relevant views of many Methodists and to define the concept of “grammatical competence”, its components and content, and to emphasize certain considerations confirmed in experiments.

In our view, grammatical competence is in fact an integral part of linguistic competence, which in turn is recognized in the methodology as an integral part of the communicative competence of a foreign language. Grammatical competence is one of the sub-competitions of foreign language communicative competence, *on the one hand*, implies the relationships and laws established between grammatical phenomena and the concepts they express, and *on the other hand*, the interrelated possibilities between the mother tongue and the studied foreign language expresses the cognitive, conceptual worldview of its representatives. In this context, many researchers are examining grammatical competence in terms of a communicative-cognitive approach to foreign language teaching; the basis of grammatical competence is based on two main types of mechanisms: *the first* is communicative, a type of mechanism that contributes to the mastery of speech in a foreign language and *the second* is a type of mechanism that stimulates cognitive, conceptual process, and thus the formation of foreign language concepts.

According to Council of Europe documents, grammatical competence refers to “the ability to know the grammatical elements of a language and apply them in speech”. Grammatical competence includes the ability to understand and express a particular meaning, formalizing it in the form of phrases and sentences structured according to certain linguistic rules (as opposed to mechanically repeating

memorized patterns)” [2, pp. 107-108]. Such an understanding of grammatical competence implies the presence of the following components:

a) Know the grammatical rules that turn lexical units into meaningful speech;

b) The ability and skills to work with grammatical devices, the adequate use of grammatical phenomena in speech activities in a foreign language in different communication situations to solve communicative problems;

c) The ability and readiness to understand and express a particular meaning, its verbal expression in oral and written form, according to the rules of a particular language [3, p. 116].

It can be seen that the structure of grammatical competence consists of three components: theoretical, linguistic and speech. However, a number of researchers, for example, L.K. Bobojanova, R.A. Budagov, G.V. Elizarova, L.I. Karpova, N.A. Kaftaylova, M.V. Lebedeva, S.G. Ter-Minasova, T.K. Tsvetkova and others emphasize the need to include the socio-cultural (sociocultural) structure in the structure of grammatical competence. Given the state of the linguo-culturological approach, linguo-didactics emphasize the importance of the connection between grammatical aspect and the culture of the country in which the language is studied, they not only contribute to the creation of a cognitive foundation but also shape the perception that different worlds they put forward. As Methodist I.V. Chernetskaya points out, the socio-cultural component of grammatical competence in the context of this approach is primarily the ability and desire of learners to differentiate between different grammatical means in the communication process to adequately convey certain communicative content to the sociocultural context of communication [4, p. 43].

The concept of an important feature of grammatical competence as an integral part of the above-mentioned foreign (English) communicative competence gives us the ability to understand and compose speech in oral and written forms, knowledge, analysis and comprehension skills, similar concepts of foreign cultural concepts in the native language and their interpretation in the process of comparison with means of expression, skills of working with grammatical means, comparison of them on the ability to use communicative problems in the process of intercultural communication” [5, pp. 80-83].

The structural basis of the process of formation and development of grammatical competence is the practical grammar of a foreign (English) language, which describes grammatical phenomena in conjunction with the tasks of forming a communicative unit. The formation of grammatical competence is carried out by combining traditional and alternative methods of teaching a foreign language at the Faculty of Foreign Philology (direction) of pedagogical universities. Certainly, both have their own tasks and goals. For example, traditional teaching methods provide for the study of English grammatical material through artificial

speech learning situations. We analyze and recommend the introduction of alternative methods of teaching, such as intensive practical training, problem-based learning, project method, modeling of communicative situations, discussion and game methods, modern information technologies and others.

In the course of the research, we tried to identify the *stages of the procedural model* of the formation of grammatical competence as an integral part of the communicative competence of a foreign English teacher. The stages of this model, identified during the study and confirmed in the experimental work, consisted of: a) primary reinforcement of the presentation and grammatical material; b) formation and automation of grammatical skills; c) communicative practice; g) control and reflection on the level of grammatical competence.

Each of these stages has its own linguistic and pedagogical features, in each of which we emphasize the use of different methods, techniques and tools to achieve specific goals and objectives. Below we have found it necessary to describe each of them separately on the basis of the author's approach.

1. The first stage in the formation of grammatical competence in future English teachers. At this stage, the focus is on the development of the knowledge component of grammatical competence, the acquisition of knowledge of grammatical rules designed to correctly compose speech in a foreign language and create an indicative basis for the formation of foreign language grammar skills in different communicative situations. At this stage, a presentation of new grammatical material is made, its linguistic features and content are revealed, and students' attention is drawn to the functioning of the grammatical structure being studied in the context of ordinary speech. Acquaintance with new grammatical materials is carried out through induction or deduction methods in educational and speech situations (exhibition (visual), foreign language context, role play, translated language tools, etc., depending on the level of linguistic success of students. In our view, we felt that this stage should not be limited to the implementation of the stated goals and objectives.

It should be noted that there is a second task of this stage, which is to strengthen the grammatical material studied by the student as a primary source in linguistic analysis exercises. We believe that the first stage of grammatical competence is formed in a student if the following tasks are given to the student for the successful completion of such exercises and their performance is strictly controlled. We found it necessary to cite some examples of the tasks identified in the course of the research and used in the experimental work: a) compare the presented situations and find commonalities and differences in the meaning of grammatical forms; b) indicate the forms of the grammatical event in the following sentences; c) state the functions of

grammatical forms in the sentence; g) explain the use of grammatical structures in the following sentences and translate them into Russian; d) select the appropriate grammatical form from the given information; e) Analyze the following examples and substantiate the rule of using a grammatical event and so on.

This type of linguistic exercise develops students' analytical thinking, and most importantly, helps to increase their ability and readiness to generalize and translate between languages based on a set goal.

2. *The second stage of formation of grammatical competence in a future English teacher.* At this stage, the student manages the grammatical structure being studied in speech situations specific to his or her activity. At this stage, the transfer of theoretical knowledge to practical foreign language activities, changing according to the communication conditions that require the formation and strengthening of grammatical skills, requires the adequacy of the grammatical color of thought. We recommend the use of the following types of linguistic exercises to achieve the stated goals and objectives:

1. *Terms of sample assignments* on the tasks of simulation exercises: a) read the sentences after the speech; b) read sentences in the form of a chorus chain; c) rewrite the following sentences, marking the grammatical form, and so on.

2. *Conditions of sample assignments* on the tasks of replacement (reserve) exercises: a) make sentences using the replacement (reserve) table; b) make sentences from the given words; c) make sentences according to the pattern; g) make sentences using the table; d) create an analog dialog; e) Answer the questions according to the samples and so on.

3. *Terms of sample assignments* on the tasks of transformational exercises: a) make a complex sentence from two simple sentences; b) translate sentences from Uzbek to English; c) give the initial sentences of the dialogue using the answers; g) tell the text using the learned grammatical structure; d) convey the content of the dialogue / polylogue in a monologue using grammatical form, etc.

We see that the goals and objectives set at the stated stage, the practical implementation of the proposed linguistic exercises prepare the ground for the formation of the linguistic component of the student, in a sense, serve as a basis.

3. *The stage of communicative practice in the formation of grammatical competence in the future English teacher.* The purpose of this stage is to further develop and improve the grammatical skills of the production and receptive foreign language, to correct, correct if possible those formed in the earlier stages, the transition from grammatical skills to grammatical skills. At this stage, communicative tasks predominate to use the activated grammatical event depending on the speech state. In order to substantiate our observations, we present the terms of the

sample assignments below and emphasize that they have been confirmed in the learning process:

- a) Read the story and act it out in dialogue;
- b) Organize an external (virtual) excursion to the city / museum for foreign visitors using Internet resources;
- c) Comment on the actions of the protagonists of the watched film;
- g) Listen to the story and explain, why ... ?;
- d) Draw a conclusion of the story using these grammatical forms, and so on.

Thus, the communicative practice phase helps the student to systematize the grammatical material being studied, allowing them to develop effective and receptive grammatical skills and abilities. The formation of grammatical competence is provided by communicative tasks, including elements of real communication and tasks in a creative form. All this to some extent prepares the ground for the formation of the grammatical component in the future English teacher, and most importantly, the development of linguistic competence.

4. *The control and expression (reflection) stage of the formation of grammatical competence in future English teachers.* This phase included the collection and analysis of information on the level of formation of students' grammatical competence, as well as the results of their own assessment of the mastered grammatical material. Depending on the complexity, different levels of control tasks are recommended, such as tests, discussions, group discussions, formal and role-playing games, project preparation, etc., to achieve the most reliable results. They are applied in practice, allowing a differential approach to control, taking into account the level of formation of grammatical competence of students. Here are some examples of control tasks used in the experimental areas of the study:

- a) Do an exercise to use the tense form of the verb;
- b) Choose the correct form of the verb in the following sentences;
- c) Organize a competition for the best knowledge of grammar;
- d) Compose questions for the grammar test;
- e) Prepare a grammar study using *Power Point* on a computer;
- f) Prepare and conduct a test on the grammatical material studied. Correct and comment on errors;
- g) Prepare a grammar table / diagram to illustrate the grammatical form using slides, etc.

The positive results of the control measures and tasks developed by us and recommended to the scientific community testified to the successful mastery of grammatical material and formed grammatical competence at this stage of teaching the grammatical aspects of a foreign (English) language. It is also important that the analysis and interpretation of negative results allows us to identify gaps in

the formation of students' grammatical competence, to correct the system of tasks in accordance with the level of formation of students' grammatical competence, led to the development of a separate “road map”.

CONCLUSION

In sum up, the process of forming the grammatical competence of a foreign (English) language becomes more relevant in the sequence of steps developed by us and tested in practice. The content, purpose and task of each subsequent stage reflected the level of formation of grammatical competence and the increasing state of the student's communicative activity in the learning and cognitive process. The tasks set in each of the highlighted stages are inextricably linked to each other, allowing them to be applied in parallel depending on the stage of teaching and the level of formation of grammatical competence.

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